

Studies on the Role of Free Oxides of Iron and Aluminium in Fixation and Transformation of Phosphate in Some Acid Soils of West Bengal

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The effect of free iron and aluminium oxides on the fixation of applied phosphates in one acid lateritic and one alluvial soil of West Bengal has been studied. It has been found that on incubation at 50% moisture holding capacity for 7 days the free oxide removed soils fix only 14.5% (lateritic soil) and 20% (alluvial soil) of the soluble phosphate added while the corresponding original soils can fix 58% and 50% respectively of the applied phosphates. The studies reveal that greater phosphate fixation in lateritic soil is due to the presence of larger amounts of free iron oxide (4.5%) and aluminium oxide (2.7%) as against 1.2% and 0.8% respectively in the alluvial soil. The phosphate fractionation studies have further indicated that the phosphates fixed as Fe-P, Al-P and reductant soluble-P in such acid soils depend almost entirely on the occurrence of the above free oxides. With the increasing period of incubation transformation of water soluble phosphates is markedly diminished by the removal of free oxides in both the soils. The free oxide removed alluvial soil has been found to fix relatively more phosphates (4.2 mg/100 gm of soil) in comparison to the corresponding lateritic one (3.51 mg/100 gm soil) on incubation for a maximum period of 60 days.

A LARGE part of the phosphorus compounds applied to soil, quickly becomes relatively unavailable to the plants. This rapid reduction in the availability of applied phosphorus is due to various physicochemical reactions of phosphorus with different components of soil. Among the various components, iron and aluminium and their free oxides are most important. A number of authors have well reviewed the role of iron and aluminium compounds in phosphate fixation in soil¹⁻³. Rajagopal and Idnani⁴ found that the free sesquioxides were responsible for high phosphate fixation in red soil of Nilgiri. DeDatta⁵ observed that the phosphate fixation in seven latosolic soils was related to the amorphous hydrated aluminium oxide content of these soils.

Dhar and Saxena⁶ reported that the applied phosphate yielded highest amount of Fe-P in acid and neutral soils and Ca-P in alkaline soils; but Al-P did not follow this trend. Kim *et al.*⁷ found that after shaking NaH_2PO_4 solution with four soils, having pH ranges 4.75-7.1 for 50 hr, the phosphorus was fixed in the soil mainly as Al-P. Khanna and Datta⁸ fertilised six soils of varying pH values with phosphate fertilisers and found that Fe-P and Al-P were present in larger amounts in acid soils.

The present investigation has been carried out with a view to study the role of free iron and aluminium oxides in fixation and transformation of added soluble phosphates in some Indian acid soils and the effect of removal of free iron and aluminium oxides on phosphate fixation.

Experimental

Two moderately acid soils of West Bengal, one from the District of Bankura (lateritic) and the other from Nadia (alluvial), were collected from plough layer (0-6"). The physico-chemical properties of the soils are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOILS

	Bankura Soil	Nadia Soil
Course sand %	24.2	9.1
Fine sand %	29.5	26.2
Silt %	25.3	35.6
Clay %	19.6	26.3
pH	5.45	5.70
Total N %	0.06	0.09
Organic carbon %	0.77	0.91
Total P (mg/100 g soil)	23.00	29.00
Exchangeable Ca (me/100 g)	4.1	8.3
Free iron oxide %	4.5	1.2
Free aluminium oxide %	2.7	0.8
C.E.C. (me/100 g)	8.6	16.8

The soils were air-dried, ground and sieved through a 80-mesh sieve. The free oxides of iron and aluminium of a part of each soil sample were removed by the method of Mehra and Jackson⁹.

The pH of the soil samples was adjusted to the original values by washing the soil with dilute HCl.

Potassium dihydrogen phosphate was used as the source of phosphorus. A 100-ppm solution of the phosphate was prepared for the desired application.

10 g portions of each soil with phosphate solution (15 mgP/100 g soil) at 50 percent moisture holding capacity were incubated at room temperature for the desired length of time. At the end of each incubation period the soil samples were taken and fractionation of soil phosphorus was carried out by the procedure of Chang and Jackson¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The amount of added phosphorus fixed by the original soil (O-soil) and the free oxides removed soil (R-soil) at different days of incubation have been given in the Table 2. The amount of the added phosphorus fixed is determined by subtracting the amount of phosphorus found in water soluble form from the amount added to the soil (i.e., 15 mgP/100 g soil).

TABLE 2—FIXATION OF ADDED PHOSPHATE IN ORIGINAL SOIL (O-SOIL) AND FREE OXIDE REMOVED SOIL (R-SOIL)

Soil	Days of incubation	O-Soil (in mg/100 g of soil)		R-Soil (in mg/100 g of soil)	
		P-in water soluble form	P-fixed	P-in water soluble form	P-fixed
Bankura	7	6.17	8.83	12.80	2.20
	20	3.42	11.58	12.00	3.00
	40	1.60	13.40	11.62	3.38
	60	0.75	14.25	11.49	3.51
Nadia	7	7.41	7.59	11.9	3.1
	20	5.25	9.75	11.5	3.5
	40	3.63	11.37	11.0	4.0
	60	2.90	12.10	10.8	4.2

Table 2 shows that after 7 days of incubation, original soil of Bankura has fixed 8.83 mg of phosphorus out of 15 mg added per 100 g of soil, i.e., about 58% of the added phosphorus has been fixed. Whereas, the free oxide removed soil has fixed only 2.2 mg of phosphorus i.e., about 14.5% of the added amount. So, the removal of free oxides of iron and aluminium causes a decrease in fixation of added phosphorus by about 43.5%.

After 7 days of incubation original soil of Nadia has fixed 7.59 mg of phosphorus i.e., about 50% of the added amount. The free oxide removed sample has fixed only 3.1 mg phosphorus i.e., about 20% of the added amount. Thus in the soil of Nadia, removal of free oxides causes a decrease on fixation of added phosphorus by about 29.5%.

From the results it is seen that the soil of Bankura has fixed more phosphorus than the soil of Nadia and removal of free oxides of iron and aluminium has caused a great decrease in phosphorus fixation capacity of both the soils but the decrease is more in the soil of Bankura.

Fixation of phosphate in acid soils is mainly due to the reaction of phosphate with iron and aluminium ions and their free oxides present in the soil. In general, three types of reaction are involved in the phosphate fixation in soils: (i) adsorption reaction, (ii) isomorphous replacement and (iii) double decomposition involving solubility product reactions. Many authors believed that iron and aluminium, which are present mostly in ionic forms in acid soils, react with soluble phosphate to form both crystalline and amorphous precipitates. Stelly and Pierre¹¹ indicated the possibility of formation of aluminium and iron phosphate minerals in acid soils.

In the present case, the soil of Bankura is slightly more acidic (pH 5.45) than the soil of (5.7) and it Nadia also contains more free iron and aluminium oxides than the soil of Nadia. So it has fixed more phosphorus. As the free oxides have imparted a great role in phosphate fixation in these acid soils, their removal has caused a great decrease in phosphate fixation capacity and the decrease is more in case of Bankura soil due to its higher content of free oxides.

The above explanation of the high phosphate fixation in acid soils can be supported by the results of the phosphate fractionation studies of the soil samples (Table 3). From the Table it is found that the added phosphorus has been fixed mainly in the form of Fe-P, Al-P and reductant soluble phosphate (Red-sol-P) in both the soils and the amounts of these forms are greater in Bankura soil than in Nadia soil. These results are in conformity with the previous supposition that soluble iron and aluminium and their free oxides greatly influence the phosphate fixation in acid soils. Similar results have been reported by Yuan *et al.*¹² and Banerjee and Mandal¹³.

The amount of Ca-P formed is very small as compared to iron-, aluminium-, and reductant-soluble-phosphates in both the soils, but the amount of Ca-P formed in Nadia soil is much more than that in Bankura soil. This is because Nadia soil, being of alluvial origin, is rather immatured and moderately weathered and it contains appreciable amount of calcium; whereas, Bankura soil is an intensively weathered lateritic one, and as a consequence, it contains only a little amount of calcium.

Table 2 shows that as the period of incubation increases, the amount of phosphorus fixed also increases, at first rapidly and then slowly in both the soils. This is probably due to the fact that the phosphorus is initially fixed by a rapid adsorption mechanism on the surface of the hydrous oxides of iron and aluminium which are formed in the process of ageing as indicated by Hsu¹⁴.

TABLE 3—TRANSFORMATION OF ADDED SOLUBLE PHOSPHATE IN O-SOIL AND R-SOIL

Soil	Days of incubation	O-Soil Phosphorus fractions (mg/100 g of Soil)					R-Soil Phosphorus fractions (mg/100 g of Soil)				
		W-S-P	Al-P	Fe-P	Ca-P	Red-sol-P	W-S-P	Al-P	Fe-P	Ca-P	Red-sol-P
Bankura	7	6.17	2.00	4.80	0.50	1.20	12.80	0.30	0.50	0.41	0.20
	20	3.42	2.63	5.60	0.55	2.40	12.00	0.36	0.55	0.50	0.64
	40	1.60	2.82	6.13	0.60	3.54	11.62	0.45	0.80	0.51	0.85
	60	0.75	2.40	6.31	0.62	4.00	11.49	0.44	0.84	0.52	0.92
Nadia	7	7.41	1.81	3.30	1.20	0.80	11.90	0.20	0.10	1.20	0.10
	20	5.25	2.20	3.80	1.50	1.70	11.50	0.30	0.15	1.40	0.55
	40	3.63	2.40	4.20	1.70	2.50	11.00	0.38	0.23	1.45	0.75
	60	2.90	2.20	4.40	1.75	2.90	10.80	0.37	0.31	1.47	0.88

After 60 days about 94% of the added phosphorus has been fixed by Bankura soil and about 80% by Nadia soil. The free oxide removed soils have fixed much less phosphorus than the original soils and the free oxide removed Nadia soil has fixed more phosphorus than free oxide removed Bankura soil. The results can also be explained by the previous supposition of the role of free oxides in phosphate fixation.

Table 3 shows that with the increase in period of incubation, the amount of added phosphorus fixed as Al-P, Fe-P or Red-sol-P has increased at first rapidly, then slowly. The amount of Ca-P has increased, but at a slower rate in comparison to the other forms. Al-P, after an initial increase, has showed a decreasing tendency after 40 days. This is probably due to the transformation of Al-P to more stable forms Fe-P and Red-sol-P since the solubility product of Fe-P is less than that of Al-P.

Table 3 also shows that after removal of free oxides of iron and aluminium, the amounts of added phosphorus fixed as Fe-P, Al-P and Red-sol-P are very little. It explains the role of above metallic oxides in the transformation of added phosphate. The amount of Ca-P, however, is not affected by free oxide removal.

It is also evident that the free oxide removed soil samples have fixed some amount of added phosphorus as Al-P, Fe-P and Red-sol-P in course of ageing.

This is probably due to the decomposition of some iron and aluminium containing minerals.

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